

Solving Quarto! (again)

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Abstract

Quarto! is an abstract board game invented around 1985 [1]. It is, in some sense, a generalised 4x4x4 variation of 3x3x1 tic-tac-toe. The game was solved in 1998 by this author. Like tic-tac-toe it is a draw. In this paper we report on a second completely independent solve, corroborating the earlier results and giving more details about the procedure.

1. Introduction

Quarto! is played on a 4 by 4 board with 16 pieces. Each piece has four binary properties: small/tall, round/square, black/white and solid/hollow. The goal of the game is to make a four-in-a-line with four pieces for any of the four binary properties. The four-in-a-line can be either on a row, on a column or on one of the two diagonals.

An important additional twist is that players do not choose their own piece from the pool of remaining pieces, but instead pick the piece the opponent needs to place next. So the game starts with one player picking a piece from the full set and giving it to the opponent. The latter then places this piece somewhere on the board and picks in turn a new piece to return.

The game was first solved by this author in 1998 and the results were then published on the internet [2]. Since then this original web page has been long removed from its hosting site. The results (perfect players will always draw, deepest win) are accepted and referred to in the internet community (e.g. Wikipedia), but were, as far as we know, never corroborated.

2. Game tree

The total size of the game tree is: $16 \cdot 16 \cdot 15 \cdot 15 \cdot \dots \cdot 1 \cdot 1 = (16!)^2 = 4.38e26$ nodes. At 100 million board evaluations per second (2026 number) traversing a tree this size would still require more than 100 billion years of computing.

In practice, using alpha-beta search will reduce the search space to approximately the square root of this number. In addition, exploiting the game's symmetries will further reduce the game tree to the point where a brute force full depth evaluation becomes feasible.

3. Symmetries

There are two types of symmetries : the ones of the board and the ones of the pieces. Note that the symmetries are with respect to the quarto evaluation function. It is any bijection on the board positions and/or the piece set that will preserve the outcome of the quarto evaluation function.

Regarding the board symmetries, any permutation of the rows ($4! = 24$) and/or of the columns ($4! = 24$) will preserve all row/column quartos, but not all of them will preserve the diagonals. In fact, of the $24 \cdot 24 = 576$ possible combinations only 16 do.

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[0, 1, 2, 3] [0, 1, 2, 3] -> [0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15] -> identity
[0, 1, 2, 3] [3, 2, 1, 0] -> [3, 2, 1, 0, 7, 6, 5, 4, 11, 10, 9, 8, 15, 14, 13, 12] -> col mirror
[0, 2, 1, 3] [0, 2, 1, 3] -> [0, 2, 1, 3, 8, 10, 9, 11, 4, 6, 5, 7, 12, 14, 13, 15] -> 0213 col swap + 0213 row swap
[0, 2, 1, 3] [3, 1, 2, 0] -> [3, 1, 2, 0, 11, 9, 10, 8, 7, 5, 6, 4, 15, 13, 14, 12] -> 0213 row swap + 3120 col swap
[1, 0, 3, 2] [1, 0, 3, 2] -> [5, 4, 7, 6, 1, 0, 3, 2, 13, 12, 15, 14, 9, 8, 11, 10] -> 1032 row swap + 1032 col swap
[1, 0, 3, 2] [2, 3, 0, 1] -> [6, 7, 4, 5, 2, 3, 0, 1, 14, 15, 12, 13, 10, 11, 8, 9] -> 032 row swap + 2301 col swap
[1, 3, 0, 2] [1, 3, 0, 2] -> [5, 7, 4, 6, 13, 15, 12, 14, 1, 3, 0, 2, 9, 11, 8, 10] -> 1302 row swap + 1302 col swap
[1, 3, 0, 2] [2, 0, 3, 1] -> [6, 4, 7, 5, 14, 12, 15, 13, 2, 0, 3, 1, 10, 8, 11, 9] -> 1302 row swap + 2031 col swap
[2, 0, 3, 1] [1, 3, 0, 2] -> [9, 11, 8, 10, 1, 3, 0, 2, 13, 15, 12, 14, 5, 7, 4, 6] -> 2031 row swap + 1302 col swap
[2, 0, 3, 1] [2, 0, 3, 1] -> [10, 8, 11, 9, 2, 0, 3, 1, 14, 12, 15, 13, 6, 4, 7, 5] -> 2031 row swap + 2031 col swap
[2, 3, 0, 1] [1, 0, 3, 2] -> [9, 8, 11, 10, 13, 12, 15, 14, 1, 0, 3, 2, 5, 4, 7, 6] -> 2301 row swap + 1032 col swap
[2, 3, 0, 1] [2, 3, 0, 1] -> [10, 11, 8, 9, 14, 15, 12, 13, 2, 3, 0, 1, 6, 7, 4, 5] -> 2301 row swap + 2301 col swap
[3, 1, 2, 0] [0, 2, 1, 3] -> [12, 14, 13, 15, 4, 6, 5, 7, 8, 10, 9, 11, 0, 2, 1, 3] -> 3120 row swap + 0213 col swap
[3, 1, 2, 0] [3, 1, 2, 0] -> [15, 13, 14, 12, 7, 5, 6, 4, 11, 9, 10, 8, 3, 1, 2, 0] -> 3120 row swap + 3120 col swap
[3, 2, 1, 0] [0, 1, 2, 3] -> [12, 13, 14, 15, 8, 9, 10, 11, 4, 5, 6, 7, 0, 1, 2, 3] -> row mirror
[3, 2, 1, 0] [3, 2, 1, 0] -> [15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0] -> col mirror + row mirror

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In addition, transposing the board will also preserve all quartos, giving an additional 16 transformations (the transpositions of the previous list).

In lexicographical order the 32 element board transformation list thus becomes :

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(0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15)
(0, 2, 1, 3, 8, 10, 9, 11, 4, 6, 5, 7, 12, 14, 13, 15)
(0, 4, 8, 12, 1, 5, 9, 13, 2, 6, 10, 14, 3, 7, 11, 15)
(0, 8, 4, 12, 2, 10, 6, 14, 1, 9, 5, 13, 3, 11, 7, 15)
(3, 1, 2, 0, 11, 9, 10, 8, 7, 5, 6, 4, 15, 13, 14, 12)
(3, 2, 1, 0, 7, 6, 5, 4, 11, 10, 9, 8, 15, 14, 13, 12)
(3, 7, 11, 15, 2, 6, 10, 14, 1, 5, 9, 13, 0, 4, 8, 12)
(3, 11, 7, 15, 1, 9, 5, 13, 2, 10, 6, 14, 0, 8, 4, 12)
(5, 1, 13, 9, 4, 0, 12, 8, 7, 3, 15, 11, 6, 2, 14, 10)
(5, 4, 7, 6, 1, 0, 3, 2, 13, 12, 15, 14, 9, 8, 11, 10)
(5, 7, 4, 6, 13, 15, 12, 14, 1, 3, 0, 2, 9, 11, 8, 10)
(5, 13, 1, 9, 7, 15, 3, 11, 4, 12, 0, 8, 6, 14, 2, 10)
(6, 2, 14, 10, 7, 3, 15, 11, 4, 0, 12, 8, 5, 1, 13, 9)
(6, 4, 7, 5, 14, 12, 15, 13, 2, 0, 3, 1, 10, 8, 11, 9)
(6, 7, 4, 5, 2, 3, 0, 1, 14, 15, 12, 13, 10, 11, 8, 9)
(6, 14, 2, 10, 4, 12, 0, 8, 7, 15, 3, 11, 5, 13, 1, 9)
(9, 1, 13, 5, 11, 3, 15, 7, 8, 0, 12, 4, 10, 2, 14, 6)
(9, 8, 11, 10, 13, 12, 15, 14, 1, 0, 3, 2, 5, 4, 7, 6)
(9, 11, 8, 10, 1, 3, 0, 2, 13, 15, 12, 14, 5, 7, 4, 6)
(9, 13, 1, 5, 8, 12, 0, 4, 11, 15, 3, 7, 10, 14, 2, 6)
(10, 2, 14, 6, 8, 0, 12, 4, 11, 3, 15, 7, 9, 1, 13, 5)
(10, 8, 11, 9, 2, 0, 3, 1, 14, 12, 15, 13, 6, 4, 7, 5)
(10, 11, 8, 9, 14, 15, 12, 13, 2, 3, 0, 1, 6, 7, 4, 5)
(10, 14, 2, 6, 11, 15, 3, 7, 8, 12, 0, 4, 9, 13, 1, 5)
(12, 4, 8, 0, 14, 6, 10, 2, 13, 5, 9, 1, 15, 7, 11, 3)
(12, 8, 4, 0, 13, 9, 5, 1, 14, 10, 6, 2, 15, 11, 7, 3)
(12, 13, 14, 15, 8, 9, 10, 11, 4, 5, 6, 7, 0, 1, 2, 3)
(12, 14, 13, 15, 4, 6, 5, 7, 8, 10, 9, 11, 0, 2, 1, 3)
(15, 7, 11, 3, 13, 5, 9, 1, 14, 6, 10, 2, 12, 4, 8, 0)
(15, 11, 7, 3, 14, 10, 6, 2, 13, 9, 5, 1, 12, 8, 4, 0)
(15, 13, 14, 12, 7, 5, 6, 4, 11, 9, 10, 8, 3, 1, 2, 0)
(15, 14, 13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0)

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For the piece symmetries there are again two kinds : inverting any subset of the properties (e.g. swap small and tall) giving $2^4 = 16$ transformations, and permuting the property order (e.g. swapping small/tall with round/square) giving $4! = 24$ transformations.

Thus in total each board has potentially $32 \cdot 16 \cdot 24 = 12,288$ equivalent boards.

Taking the above into account there are only 148 unique game configurations with two pieces placed and a third gifted, a sizeable reduction from $16 \cdot 16 \cdot 15 \cdot 15 \cdot 14 / 2! = 403,200$. Table 1 lists the number of unique game configurations and the approximate reduction with respect to the naive number for the first few levels

level	unique	total	gain
1+1	8	3840	480
2+1	148	403200	~2700
3+1	3382	24460800	~7200
4+1	91746	953971200	~10400

Table 1: unique game configurations

4. Search results

The primary goal of this exercise is to establish whether Quarto! can be won when played perfectly (either by the first move player or the second move player). If this is not the case, i.e. if perfect players can always force a draw, the next interesting question becomes how early any win can be forced. A related question is up until which point in the game it does not really matter what you play.

Due to Quarto!'s special twist, we need a special unambiguous way to 'count' how deep we are in the game (the plies). A 0+1 configuration means with the first piece chosen by the first player and no pieces yet on the board. The next level is 1+1 with one piece chosen and one on the board. The game eventually ends with a 16+0 configuration (or possibly sooner with a N+0 configuration).

Based on the above we can already make a rough estimate of the task at hand (using expected alpha-beta performance of $n!$ and node processing speed of 100 million nodes per second (MNPS))

level	unique	alphabeta	search time	total
0+1	1	21T	58 h	58h
1+1	8	1308B	218 m	29h
2+1	148	87B	870 s	36h
3+1	3382	6B	60 s	56h
4+1	91746	479M	5 s	127h

Table 2: estimated search time for alpha-beta

Searching a few hundreds of random 4+1 games quickly yields a (non-trivial) 4+1 win like the one below

0000	----	0001	----	
0110	----	----	1110	
----	----	----	----	
----	----	----	----	
				0010
play on 1 give 1111				

Figure 1: example 4+1 win

leaving just the task of checking whether any of the levels above have any wins.

Checking all 148 unique 2+1 games shows that all of them are a draw. Consequently, both players can always force a draw when playing perfectly. Like tic-tac-toe, just less obviously. In addition, checking all 3382 unique 3+1 games shows that all of them are either a draw or a trivial win. So there are no non-trivial wins above level 4+1.

5. Code optimisation

The total search time is the product of the number of game tree nodes visited, times the time to evaluate the node plus the average per node overhead to create/maintain the game tree.

Concerning the number of nodes visited, just plain alpha-beta already does an almost perfect job at pruning the game tree. A substantial additional average pruning improvement can be trivially gained by visiting the board positions in diagonals first order. Intuitively the pieces on the diagonals are part of three lines (the other pieces of just two) and hence in a way more decisive.

Other common game tree optimisations however yielded only marginal tree reductions at best, and usually at a substantial extra overhead cost, resulting in an overall slowdown instead of speed-up.

For the board evaluation function, one trivial optimisation is to check only the lines containing the last position played. This will then be a two/three term OR, each term an OR of the eight properties, each of these an AND of the four positions in the line. Calculating this nested boolean expression can be sped up by allowing the CPU to calculate as much as possible of it in parallel, exploiting the fact that modern CPUs can perform multiple operations in parallel (pipelines). In addition, they can perform logical operations on 64 bits in one go, so packing more state in larger integers can yield substantial gains. E.g. it might be beneficial to represent the boolean properties not with a single bit (0 or 1), but with two bits (01 and 10). This way a single AND can test all four properties and their four complements in one go.

The tree traversal overhead consists of keeping track of the search tree state, either in global variables or variables on the stack (functions' parameters and local variables). Keeping track of more state can avoid some computation, but at the cost of other computation and more memory. However, using more memory can come with important speed degradation due to its interaction with the cache levels between the CPU and RAM. In the end, the fastest solution will be the one best aligned with the CPU at hand.

One optimisation worth mentioning separately is related with the fact that at each level of the game tree you need to iterate over all remaining pieces and positions. In case of a trivial loop over all pieces/positions guarded with a not-yet-used test, most of these tests will return false as you deepen the tree. Several contemporary CPUs allow for an efficient calculation of the number of trailing zeroes for an integer value. A well-known code idiom can exploit this feature to efficiently go through only the available pieces/positions by representing them as a 16 bit integer mask.

6. Code redundancy and performance

When solving a problem with a program, there is always the chance that the code you used is incorrect and hence possibly also the results it produced. To maximise the probability that the new results are not affected by a code defect, this time we used three independent implementations of the solver. All versions were written in C. One was hand-coded (but unrelated to the 1998 code) and two other versions were generated by two leading contemporary AI coding assistants (Anthropic's Claude and Google's Gemini 3.1 Pro). The prompts to the AI tools included what optimisations to use, but no implementation details.

The three versions intentionally use an increasing very small set of simple/straightforward optimisations:

hand-coded : alpha-beta, diagonal first, partial quarto check

Claude : negamax, diagonal first, partial quarto check

Gemini : negamax, diagonal first, partial quarto check expanded and in-lined, trailing zeroes plus availability bit mask

resulting in respective speeds of 70 MNPS, 90 MNPS and 160 MNPS.

At 160 MNPS, checking all 3382 3+1 games on an 8-core M2 processor took less than 10 hours. All versions of the code reported identical results across all runs.

7. Conclusions and comparison

The main results from the original 1998 web page were corroborated :

the game is a draw

the deepest win is at 4+1

and the corollaries :

on level 3+1 it suffices to look for a DRAW

on level 2+1 and above, it does not matter what you play

The 1998 solve exploited far less symmetries than possible as no attempt was made to find all of them systematically. This does not invalidate the 1998 results, as the ones that were used were correct. The symmetries are comprehensively studied in [3]. For 2+1 and 3+1 configurations the number of unique games calculated in [3] was readily reproduced. For 4+1 configurations [3] mentions 91558 unique configurations, while we generated 91746. The difference corresponds exactly with the 188 configurations that already form a quarto with the four pieces on the board.

The 1998 solve mentioned that approximately only about 1 in 1000 4+1 configurations resulted in a non-trivial win. The more precise estimate found in this solve is closer to 3 percent. Checking all unique 91746 4+1 configurations yielded 2959 non-trivial wins.

References

[1] [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quarto_\(board_game\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quarto_(board_game))

[2] Quarto, L.Goossens, 1998. (<https://web.archive.org/web/20041012023358/http://ssel.vub.ac.be/Members/LucGoossens/quarto/quartotext.htm>)

[3] An exploration of Gameplay in Quarto, M. Kerner and D. Angluin, 2001. (<https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/quarto-55043713/55043713>)